
Final PhD Thesis Report

EnvDis

Modelling the influence of weather
and climate in human disease:
salmonellosis today and tomorrow

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INTRODUCTION

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1. PhD Project team composition

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2. Abstract

The environmental component of the *One Health* approach is increasingly recognized as essential in addressing emerging health challenges. The seasonal pattern observed in the incidence of certain infectious diseases motivated to frame weather as an important factor driving cases and question its power to predict incidence. Using salmonellosis as an example, this thesis explored the main weather factors driving disease in England and Wales and assessed the suitability of forecasting salmonellosis from weather data in a different spatial location as well as a different weather scenario.

The novelty of this study lies in the comprehensive exploration of the effect of 13 weather factors, at high spatio-temporal linkage, stratified in different combinations, which challenges other studies of single parameters in a silo. The good performance observed when reproducing the empirical data is a validation of the methodology. Without fitting the data, this approach enables drawing objective conclusions from complex weather interactions, facilitating the investigation of relevant factors influencing in human salmonellosis incidence, such as different weather factors alone and in combination, the effect of temperature in bacterial growth in food as well as characterisation of the universality of short-term weather and long-term climate to influence salmonellosis incidence.

The research presented contributes to existing knowledge on the effect of weather and climate as modulators of disease, which is widely accepted but under-investigated. The methodology developed identified maximum air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, dewpoint temperature, daylength and global radiation as some of the most relevant weather factors driving salmonellosis, and more importantly, characterised the influence each combination exerts on the incidence of disease. While not delving into the underlying mechanisms behind the effect of weather, the knowledge generated from this thesis contributes to generate hypotheses regarding mechanisms of disease co-occurrence with weather and lays the groundwork for future predictive tools.

The open source code can be easily adapted to other infectious agents, where enough data is available. Interested stakeholders would be interested in performing quick and routinary checks on their main diseases of concern, especially in case of extraordinary weather events are expected, in order to be better prepared an allocate health resources accordingly.

3. Introduction and Objectives

The global population has more than tripled its size since 1950 and, according to the latest projections by the United Nations, is expected to reach 10.4 billion in 2100. This 30% increase from current population levels is attributed to variations in fertility rates across different countries and continued reduction in mortality rates (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs 2022). The inevitable consequences of an increased human population, such as food insecurity, environmental

degradation, and closer contact with wildlife, pose a significant risk for the emergence of new and re-emerging diseases. Hence, the need to explore the role of weather as a key component of the *One Health* approach.

The association between disease and weather dates to Hippocrates (460-378 BC), who wrote about a common link between disease and the environment: air, water quality and season of the year (Hippocrates 1911). This conception has been consolidated with the advances in weather forecast and the availability of high-resolution predictions, motivating the development of predictive models. From the patterns observed in salmonellosis notifications in the past 29 years in England and Wales, a peak is systematically observed in late summer. This led to the main research question: **what is the role of weather and climate in the incidence of salmonellosis disease?** Weather and climate have a different influence over salmonellosis. While weather refers to the conditions of the atmosphere over a short period of time (i.e. weeks and months), climate is the cumulative result of weather over longer periods of time (usually years or decades).

Multiple interacting factors are involved in the seasonality of diseases, often entailing a time lag. The increase of salmonellosis cases appears to be associated with higher temperatures, albeit other environmental factors could be involved. The exact contribution of each weather factor as well as its relative impact on the disease is not well known. Modelling is applied in this context to provide a better and detailed understanding on the role of weather as modulator of salmonellosis disease and how it relates to higher bacterial counts in food. I will go back in the available incidence data to the estimated day of infection and identify the weather conditions related to the increases in cases and hypothesise about the causes.

In principle, modelling the drivers of infection would be an appropriate approach, as infection is a precursor of disease. However, the data analysed in this thesis only include lab-confirmed symptomatic cases, i.e. disease events. Therefore, laboratory-diagnosed disease will be used as a proxy for infection. While many studies exploring the relationship between weather and disease tend to focus on temperature and relative humidity –two essential physical requirements for microbial growth–, this thesis takes a more comprehensive approach. It evaluates a wide range of relevant weather factors and characterises the simultaneous effect of multiple factors on the incidence of salmonellosis. Additionally, it assesses the effect of temperature on relevant food sources associated with the disease.

In terms of future scenarios, the WHO states that an increase in temperature or duration of high-temperature episodes may promote greater multiplication of *Salmonella* in foodstuff (WHO 2018). More specifically, EFSA has estimated an increase of about 20,000 cases of salmonellosis over the next decade in Europe (EFSA 2020). The model developed in this thesis is used to better understand the impact of climate change on the incidence and distribution of salmonellosis cases.

Salmonella enterica was chosen for this research due to its significant social and economic impact, as outbreaks continue to occur despite preventive measures being implemented. In addition to this, the availability of large amount of data collected over many years made it an ideal choice. The high-resolution nature of the data played an instrumental role in building the model and drawing robust conclusions. While the analysis is limited to human data due to restricted access to animal data, it is acknowledge that efforts to integrate both types of data are of great interest.

The importance of the study lies in the fact that diseases are dynamic processes that require extensive knowledge to control. Understanding disease-specific seasonal patterns is important in designing and improving intervention strategies. The aim of this research is to contribute to the understanding of the role of weather and climate in seasonal and spatio-temporal fluctuations in the incidence of salmonellosis in humans. To achieve this, I set the following objectives:

- **Review existing knowledge** on non-typhoidal salmonellosis in humans, sources of infection, the effect of weather and climate modulating microbial growth and disease incidence, as well as common approaches used to model this relationship.
- Investigate the **effect of temperature on the growth of *Salmonella* in the main foodstuffs** associated with salmonellosis and the relevance it has on the overall incidence in humans. A mechanistic approach was used for this.
- **Identify relevant weather factors** and their interconnected influence on the number of salmonellosis cases reported in England and Wales. A statistical model was developed to assess the power of weather in driving salmonellosis cases.
- **Test the universality of the effect of weather** on salmonellosis, regardless of geographical location. The statistical model was applied to the incidence data from a different country from the one in which it was originally developed.
- Estimate the **impact that climate change** may have on the patterns of salmonellosis incidence in the near future (2043) in England and Wales.

The expected impact is to be foundation for future experimental research focusing on the main weather factors and their influence on disease. Other diseases, quick easy estimation of disease incidence and better preparedness.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1 Data

To build the model, we used daily national surveillance data of confirmed salmonellosis cases reported to the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) in England and Wales during 2000-2016. For further validation of the model, we used daily cases reported to the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment in the Netherlands (RIVM) during 2015-2019. In both countries, a case was culture-confirmed by a diagnostic laboratory, with the difference that in England and Wales notification of non-typhoid salmonellosis is mandatory (UK Health Security Agency 2022) while in the Netherlands is voluntary (Chanamé Pinedo et al. 2022). Surveillance of salmonellosis cases relies on medical doctors and laboratories to notify suspected and confirmed cases. Further details regarding surveillance and diagnostic methods have been published elsewhere for the UK (Wheeler et al. 1999) and NL (Chanamé Pinedo et al. 2022). The reported cases were filtered by selecting *Salmonella* subspecies of foodborne interest (i.e. *Salmonella* sp. *Enterica* ssp. *Enterica*.) and excluding cases with confirmed travel history or unknown patient residence. Where a same patient was re-assessed for an on-going salmonellosis diagnosis, only the first recorded instance was accounted for in a 3-month window.

In the UK, for the years 2000 to 2016, we assumed a relatively constant human behaviour, including the absence of significant control strategies that would imply a variable case-reporting rate. The study period was intentionally selected to begin two years after the implementation of mandatory poultry

vaccination in the UK in 1998, and to conclude in 2016 with the latest year for which small-scale demographic data was available to us. However, there is still a difference in the number of cases recorded for these 17 years of study, with a smooth downward trend from the year 2000. This difference could be related to reasons other than a true decrease in the number of infections, giving a erroneous correlation with certain weather conditions (e.g., higher rate of outbreaks, travel-related cases, awareness campaigns, etc.). To remove this “external” effect from our data, we removed the mean of the cases data to keep only the periodicity (“detrending”). (Gama Dessavre et al. 2019) suggested that detrending using the mean improves substantially the predictions, correcting for reporting bias, as well as the human behaviour and other unknown factors influencing the number of cases reported. The “detrended cases” result in a seasonal time series with global mean equal to one.. To make the results more interpretable, we multiplied the detrended time series by the yearly average of cases reported for the last 5 years (around 15 daily cases for the years 2011-2016). The detrended cases were used to calculate the conditional incidence discussed in section 2.3, from the selected weather parameters.

Catchment areas in England and Wales were defined as the area around the 216 diagnostic laboratories to which it provides coverage, but are subject to change as population and transportation infrastructure changes in time. The number of residents in each catchment area were estimated by calculating the occurrence of each LSOA (Lower Layer Super Output Areas, the smallest demographic unit created by the Office for National Statistics) per postcode of the diagnostic laboratories. The resident information was used to calculate the estimated number of salmonellosis incidence in a catchment area. Salmonellosis cases were linked to the local weather conditions of the catchment areas due to patient data protection and assuming that patients would attend the nearest laboratory to their usual residence. The differences of temperature and rainfall between the patient home address and the laboratory is known to be small (Djennad et al. 2018) and assumed this is the case for other weather factors too.

Daily weather parameters were downscaled to the postcode of the diagnostic laboratories –and assigned to the corresponding catchment area– via the Met Office via the Medical and Environmental Data Mash-up Infrastructure (MEDMI) platform (<http://tools.data-mashup.org.uk/medmi/>) (“MEDMI Website Launches - European Centre for Environment and Human Health | ECEHH” n.d.). Ten weather parameters were selected for their relevance to the multiplication of *Salmonella* in the food product after leaving the point of sale, that is, when the food product is subject to weather variations outside a controlled environment. Subsequently, maximum (Tmax) and mean air temperature (Tmean), temperature variation (Tmax-Tmin), dew point temperature, surface air pressure, relative humidity, mean precipitation, cumulative precipitation over the time lag chosen, sunshine duration, global radiation and day length were explored in different combinations. Given that people remain a good part of the day indoors in the UK, we also assessed the effect of indoor temperature and humidity conditions in the incidence of salmonellosis from the equations developed in Verheyen and Bourouiba (Verheyen and Bourouiba 2022) based on outdoor Tmean and RH values and an presumed thermal comfort of 21°C.

4.2 Adjustment for delays in reported cases and weather variables

To account for the ensemble of weather conditions that may have a cumulative effect on the occurrence of a disease event (e.g., effect on the bacterial community and/or people behaviour), a rolling mean of the weather conditions 7 days prior to the day of infection was used. Other lags of 2,

14 and 21 days were explored with no significant improvement of the model performance. Additionally, to link the meteorological conditions at the time of exposure to an infective bacterial load, a probable day of infection was estimated from the specimen date (the date the specimen was collected from the patient) after correcting for the incubation period and reporting delays (time to seek medical healthcare and sample delay). The incubation period was drawn by a gamma distribution from the mean incubation periods of the three most common serotypes reported to UKHSA (Enteritidis, Typhimurium and Virchow, which makes up to 75% of our cases), and the mean incubation periods of the remaining 19 serotypes studied by Eikmeier et al. (Eikmeier, Medus, and Smith 2018) as a proxy of the other ~900 serotypes that accounted for the 25% of our cases. For the three major serotypes, the mean and the variance were used to calculate the shape and scale parameters of the gamma distribution. The mean and mode (mode= 30.2 hours) were used for the rest of the serotypes. The time to healthcare (1-5 days UK, 0-3 for blood samples, and 7-11 for stool samples in NL) and sample delay (0-1 UK, 0-2 NL) adapted to the country of study were drawn from a log-normal distribution, from available estimations (Bonačić Marinović et al. 2015; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 2015) and expert opinion (Nichols, Mughini-Gras, and Pijnacker personal communication). An additional delay was included for the NL from the time for a sample to get to the RIVM (1-2 days for blood, and 1-3 for stool samples).

4.3 Statistical analysis

The methodology used in this paper builds on the conditional incidence developed by Lo Iacono et al, 2022 (Lo Iacono et al. 2020). The approach comprises two main steps: i) *evaluation of the incidence salmonellosis conditional to the weather factors* and ii) *generation of the time-series of cases based on the local weather factors and number of residents*.

4.3.1 Evaluation of the incidence salmonellosis conditional to the weather factors.

We first selected a combination of weather factors of interest e.g., maximum air temperature, precipitation and global radiation. Here we focused on three weather factors simultaneously. For numerical convenience the values of the weather factors were divided into discrete bins. We then selected all the situations in the entire dataset (i.e., irrespectively of location and time) that corresponded to a each possible combination of weather factors averaged over a certain number of past days. For example, all situations when the average value of the maximum air temperature in the last 7 days was equal between 15 and 16 degrees, the average precipitation was between 0 and 1 mm, and the average global radiation was between 1000 and 1500 Wm⁻². We then calculated the total number of cases found for that specific weather combination, divided by the total number of residents exposed to the same weather conditions (Eq 1). Unusual weather combinations leading to a situation with a total residents exposed to the said combination was less than 1,000,000 were considered non representative and removed from the analysis.

$$P_{cond} = \frac{\text{Number infected people}}{\text{Number people exposed to the same weather variables}} \quad (1).$$

The ratio P_{cond} is interpreted as the conditional probability of detecting a case given the specific weather values. Here and throughout, by *conditional incidence* we refer to the daily probability of detecting a salmonellosis case multiplied by one million, representing the daily number of cases per million.

4.3.2 Simulation of the time-series of cases based on the local weather factors and number of residents.

The conditional incidence estimated above was used to simulate the time-series of cases, *viz.* to calculate the expected number of cases at a particular location given the weather factors. Cases were assumed as random occurrences given that the causal factors are too numerous to be quantified, with a negligible human-to-human transmission. Therefore, the number of salmonellosis cases is governed by a Poisson process with a rate equal to the expected daily number of salmonellosis cases in each catchment area. The rate was calculated by ascertaining the weather factors in a catchment area, estimating the corresponding conditional probability, and multiplying it by the number of residents living in the said area. The stochastic nature of weather factors contributes to the variability in the conditional incidence rate, reproducing the natural overdispersion of the data. Consequently, by solely considering the weather records for each day and location, we can effectively reproduce the number of detected cases. The comparison of the modelled expected number of cases and historical lab-confirmed reported cases allowed to assess the performance of the model for different weather factors combinations.

4.4 Validation in the Netherlands

A comparative study was carried out to test the hypothesis that the effect of weather on salmonellosis cases, represented by the conditional incidence, is universal and not specific to geographical location. The conditional incidence was calibrated using a comprehensive 17-year dataset of daily surveillance data from England and Wales. This calibrated incidence was applied to weather records in the Netherlands and the corresponding resident information in a 5km grid resolution to estimate the expected number of salmonellosis cases in each location. Finally, we compared the predictions from the model with their reported numbers. Laboratory-confirmed salmonellosis cases reported to the RIVM for the years 2015, and 2017 to 2019 were compared to the modelled cases conditional to one of the best-performing weather combination identified from the results of England and Wales. The year 2016 was not included in the validation with the Dutch cases due to a disproportionately higher observed cases linked to a multicounty outbreak (Pijnacker et al. 2019). At the same time, the year 2020 was dismissed due to its reporting singularity linked to the COVID-19 pandemic. The rest of the outbreak data were kept, including as much case information as possible to test the model. The weather data was downloaded from the Netherlands Royal Meteorological Institute open-source platform (KNMI: <https://www.knmi.nl/klimaat>). The residents information was downloaded from Statistics Netherlands (CBS: <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb>) at full 6-digit postal code level (PC6). All the data were harmonised at a 5km grid resolution. Values at both upper and lower ends of weather registered in the Netherlands that had not a corresponding matching value in the UK were removed from the analysis. This implied a 2.5% of the total Dutch weather data whose conditional incidence could not be determined.

5. Scientific Results and Discussion

The performance of the model for different weather factors was assessed visually by comparing the empirical cases with the reconstruction of the modelled cases averaged for all the years studied. No quantitative operator was used given that the subtle and varied performance of the different weather combinations cannot be captured by a test. Furthermore, each factor has a different scale, is measured with different units and have more constant values (e.g. humidity) than others (e.g. of radiation), penalising a natural variability by a coefficient that only looked at the similarity of the curves. The

analogous visual agreement of the simulations with empirical data validated the suitability of our model, and pointed to maximum and mean air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, and global radiation as important explanatory variables in England and Wales. Daylength proved to be a good proxy for global radiation where necessary. At the same time, the astronomical nature of the day length implies reduced variability and measurement errors. Other variable combinations and time lags were explored with less to no relevance.

5.1 Results from England and Wales

The model reproduced the main seasonal peak of salmonellosis incidence between August and September. Out of the various weather factors examined, the simulations utilizing the combination of mean air temperature, relative humidity, and day length demonstrated a strong correlation with historical salmonellosis records, which are considered the gold standard. This finding highlights the suitability of these factors for effectively estimating the risk of salmonellosis in specific areas. Other weather factor combinations also showed good predictive power, and are discussed as part of the supplementary material of the main thesis. Outdoors weather conditions exhibited a better agreement than the estimated indoor values. The model was considered suitable for providing an estimate of the risk of salmonellosis for England and Wales from weather forecasts.

The effect of the different weather combinations on the risk of contracting salmonellosis is discussed in detail together with line plots in the thesis. A generalized higher risk for mean temperatures between 10-20°C, followed by a decrease for greater temperatures. The risk was also higher for longer days, but not the longest (i.e. June and July). The combined values of day length and mean temperature that posed a higher risk were typical for March to October for the studied dates. Relative humidity did not seem to have a relevant influence by itself, given that all the profile values in the figure were overlapping without a different pattern for the different values.

5.2 Results from the application of the model in the Netherlands

The main summer seasonal trend is captured in the reconstruction of the time series. The model also projects a smooth decline of the peak until September resulting in greater number of salmonellosis cases as compared to the reported ones. However, the model also produces isolated spikes not observed in the empirical data, especially in June, and identifies an overall 25% of underreporting of cases over the entire series. This outcome suggests that the effect of weather on salmonellosis incidence is not limited to a specific geographical location but rather has a universal effect.

5.3 Results from the application of the model in a climate change scenario

The conditional incidence was applied to the near-future climate projections up until 2043. Land projections were downloaded at daily, 60km-grid resolution for the 15 members or possible scenarios produced by the global climate model HadGEM3-GC3.05 (Met Office Hadley Centre, 2018) for the RCP 8.5, available for bulk download at <http://data.ceda.ac.uk/badc/ukcp18/data/land-rcm/uk/country/rcp85/3>. Each projection provides an example of climate variability in a changing climate, which is consistent across many climate variables at different times and spatial locations. Annual population projections by regions were downloaded from NOMIS for England, and from StatsWales for Wales in a shapefile format.

Overall, i) the current summer seasonality is split in two in August and September, with an increasingly pronounced trough in between them. This phenomenon does not seem to be explained by temperature, since temperature is projected to be continuously higher from June to November. However the average precipitation during August and September are lower than the historical records. On top of the double peak, ii) a smooth increase in modelled cases is detectable at the end of May for all years as well as iii) a crest at the end of April in 2040. Both events coincide with decreased average rain projections. By 2043 a flattening effect is observed, levelling out the historically marked peak of September with a iv) smooth increase in cases from January to April and v) from April to mid June. These events coincide with an increase in predicted temperature and precipitation. The subsequent vi) decline in cases in the month of July match with decreased precipitations. It is pending to determine whether the model predicts an overall decrease in the total number of cases as compared to the current level of observed cases.

5.4 Discussion

The nature of the estimations are defined by the data available. Ideally, the approach should be based on actual data of infection instead of reported data. Here, we assume that reporting bias is not significantly affected by weather factors. At the same time, the reporting habits are considered constant.

The time series reconstruction obtained from the model with relevant weather factors reproduced the main peak of empirical salmonellosis incidence between August and September in England and Wales. This is a validation of the methodology and a confirmation of **the strong influence of weather on salmonellosis disease**. At the same time, the model identified combinations of weather variables with a relevant influence on the incidence of salmonellosis and characterized their effect.

The reconstruction of most of the combinations explored worked well as predictors of disease, suggesting that multiple weather factors alone and in combination have a relevant role driving salmonellosis incidence in humans. Moreover, the **universal effect of weather** was demonstrated by the favourable outcomes achieved when applying the model in the Netherlands. Although food is often consumed indoors, the results of the model for indoor environment conditions revealed that outdoor weather values yielded better results in reproducing the empirical cases. Nonetheless, other environmental factors not accounted for in this study could have a decisive role in infection.

Some limitations of the model include sample and observation bias. Human behaviour (medical seeking, case notification, eating habits, etc.) are unavoidably linked to incidence data and this cannot be detached from the data with certainty. This bias is included in the data and hence, the methodology assumes that no major behaviour changes in the years of study. Another limitation of our statistical approach is its reduced predicting power in novel weather scenarios. The model was fed from weather records in the past and is unable to function under novel weather conditions that have not been recorded previously. In consequence, the model can only give meaningful information where situations recorded in the past increase their frequency, with the rest of the unprecedented conditions not showing any result and removed from the analysis.

Despite this, we considered that the application of the model in assessing the impact of climate change in human salmonellosis can offer a valuable output based on the best data available to date. According to the UKCP18 forecasts, wetter winters and drier summers are expected, with a particular impact in

southern England (Bernie et al., 2018). If the impact of weather on the incidence of salmonellosis were linear, a notable increase in cases in summer in the coming years would be expected. Interestingly, our model based on the effect of weather from empirical cases does not forecast this. By 2043 in England and Wales there may be not only one seasonal incidence peak in summer, but up to two peaks in August and September, and an increased reporting of cases during the first half of the year. However, considering the uncertainty surrounding climate projections, it is more prudent to emphasize the analysis of salmonellosis incidence patterns rather than placing excessive reliance on the precise magnitude of the predicted cases.

The model allows to estimate salmonellosis notifications based on weather forecast. However, the main contribution of the analysis is the detailed insight of different weather interactions and how they are related with salmonellosis incidence, which is not always evident nor linear. To date, this is the first study that analyses the interconnected effect of multiple weather factors (other than commonly studied temperature and rainfall), at high spatio-temporal resolution, on the risk of salmonellosis and in the context of climate change. This information could be used by health professionals and Public Health officers to be more alert to the potential increase in cases and outbreaks at unusual times of the year, allowing early detection and preventive measures to be taken.

6. Conclusions and Future work and perspectives

The model developed in this thesis describes the effect that weather has in salmonellosis incidence conditional to specific weather and climate factors. Given the co-dependencies of the different weather variables, the novelty of this study lies in the comprehensive exploration of the effect of 14 weather factors at high spatio-temporal linkage, stratified in different combinations, which challenges other studies of single parameters in a silo. Moreover, the model also accounts for relevant particularities of the infectious agent (i.e., incubation period) and the delays involved in case reporting (e.g., time to seek health care), which allows to identify a subset of weather conditions around a likely day of infection. The approach is **applicable for other geographic locations** provided that long-term high-resolution data is available, **and adaptable to other infectious diseases**. The universal effect of weather was broadly demonstrated after applying the model built with data from England and Wales to the Netherlands. However, this conclusion would be strengthened if the model is applied to a country with social and climatic conditions that are most opposite to the UK, such as a country from a different continent and hemisphere.

The model allows to estimate salmonellosis notifications based on weather forecast. When looking at the effect of climate change on the incidence of salmonellosis, changes in trend and seasonality are to be expected. This knowledge is essential for disease preparedness and prevention, especially with regard to the increasing anthropogenic impact on the environment and climate change. However, the main contribution of this work lies in the detailed insight of the effect of different weather interactions and how they are related with salmonellosis cases, which is not always evident nor linear. While the contribution of the conditional incidence to the existing knowledge on *Salmonella* is still phenomenological, it **helps to formulate theories around the mechanism underlying the interface seasonality-disease**. As future research, we recommend a complementary mechanistic approach where the effect of the different weather variables acts in the biologic processes of *Salmonella* are available. The conditional incidence could be applied in conjunction with in-depth experimental and social research to infer robust mechanistic theories. For example, to test the hypothesis of salmonellosis infection driven by outdoor barbecues on a warm day, we can couple it with extensive

retail chicken sales data. These theories could be then used to feed a theoretical agent-based model and compared with the conditional incidence for acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis.

6.1 References

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7. PhD project self-evaluation

The main objective of investigating the environment as a modulator of salmonellosis incidence in humans was broadly achieved. Different approaches (mechanistic, spatial, statistical), as well as several environmental drivers were explored (weather conditions, land use, animal presence, farming systems). Due to data availability, the focus was laid on the weather component, and in depth analysis were performed (time lags, evaluation of weather factors in different combinations, climate change effect), resulting in the creation and validation of the conditional incidence model as the main output of the thesis.

The performance of the model with surveillance data from a different geography was planned to be done in New Zealand. However, given the uncertainty in international travel due to the COVID-19 pandemic, a short-term visit to the National Health Institute of the Netherlands was scheduled instead. The model built with UK data was applied to Dutch salmonellosis surveillance data, testing the universal effect of weather as shown with the model, as well as identifying improvements to the methodology (i.e. feeding the model with years with comparable incidence rates, normalization discrepancies, etc.) and strengthening the results.

The initial project proposal mentioned the application of the model in Leptospirosis. However, efforts were focused in giving more solid results on the Salmonella-weather interface with a deeper exploration and improvement of the model, benefiting from the high-resolution weather data. Nonetheless, the model was written in a generic fashion and the source code is publicly available so that it can be adapted to other infectious agents, where adequate resolution data is available. The results define the probable incidence for a certain day and location given the forecasted weather. Therefore, both direct and indirect effect of the weather factors with greater influence over human salmonellosis are presented graphically, which require a detailed and careful interpretation.

Finally, the educational side the project satisfactorily met my expectations. Through research development courses, attending scientific conferences, networking with experts, and discussing research gaps with peers and supervisors, I consider to have substantially grown as a scientist, confident of my critical thinking and able to expose scientific results in an accurate manner. I have also gained valuable coding and disease modelling knowledge that will guide my professional career as a risk modeller in a public health agency.

8. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

(Next page)

Deliverables

PhD reference	PhD Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered (month)	Comments	Integrative categories*
PhD11-FBZ4/5-EnvDis	D-PhD11-1.1	Mandatory Trainings	M30	M30	https://zenodo.org/record/4516634#.ZFpIK3bMI2w	
	D-PhD11-1.2	Presentation of findings (e.g. conferences, internal school seminars) Y1	M36	M35	https://zenodo.org/record/4516634#.ZFpIK3bMI2w	
	D-PhD11-1.3	Attending Relevant Training courses Y1	M36	M36	https://zenodo.org/record/4516634#.ZFpIK3bMI2w	
	D-PhD11-1.4	End of Year Confirmation Report Y1	M39	M46	https://zenodo.org/record/5562226#.ZFpJQ3bMI2w	
	D-PhD11-2.1	Presentation of findings (e.g. conferences, internal school seminars) Y2	M46	M47	https://zenodo.org/record/5593107#.ZFpImXbMI2w	
	D-PhD11-2.2	End of Year Progress Review Y2	M48	M48	https://zenodo.org/record/5786572#.ZFpIqHbMI2w	
	D-PhD11-3.1	Presentation of findings (e.g. conferences, internal school seminars) Y3	M60	M60	https://zenodo.org/record/7320381#.ZFpIv3bMI2w	
	D-PhD11-3.2	End of Year Progress Review Y3	M60	M60	https://zenodo.org/record/7323971#.Y3OwdnbP2Uk	
	D-PhD11-3.3	Completion/Submission of thesis	M60	Due M66	Accumulated delays derived from COVID	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

PhD reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	Achieved	Comments
PhD11-FBZ4/5-EnvDis	M-PhD11-1	Test and discuss findings of the model for Salmonellosis	M48	M35	Yes	Included in Deliverable 1.2
	M-PhD11-2	Validate the model with data from another European country	M55	M54	Yes	Public: https://zenodo.org/record/7271613#.Y3T1iXbP02w
	M-PhD11-3	Write up thesis	M60	Due M72	Ongoing	Public link to be shared after corrections on final thesis done

9. Interactions with JRPs/JIPs or with external (global, EU, national or regional) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), national and international surveillance programmes.

- Online assistance to the JIP COHESIVE final meeting on 8-10/11/2021 for learning on the collaborative strategies between human, veterinary food and environment.
- Follow up on the outcomes on the JPRs DISCOVER and ADONIS for including relevant and up-to-date findings on *Salmonella* in EnvDis
- Participation to the OHEJP Summer school in 2021 and 2022
- Assistance and poster presentation on the progress of the project on the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting in 2020, 2021 and 2022.
- Assistance to workshops organised by the OHEJP:
 - o 6th Cogwheel workshop (SafeConsume) on 25/11/2020,
 - o 7th Cogwheel workshops (Versatile Emerging infectious disease Observatory (VEO) and Monitoring Outbreak events for Disease surveillance in a data science context (MOOD) on 25/02/2021,
 - o Communications and media workshop on 5-6/10/2020,
 - o integrate approaches to zoonoses – COHESIVE project on 8/10/2021, and
 - o Professional Development module (BfR) on 15-19/02/2021.
- Invitation to present the EnvDis project on the 6th cogwheel workshop of OHEJP and SafeConsume on 25/11/2020

10. Interactions with OHEJP stakeholders

- [Short-Term Mission](#) at the RIVM within the gastrointestinal disease group, for an exchange of expertise, methods and collaborative paper.
- Liaise with UKSHA *Salmonella* and gastroenteric experts for exchange of ideas (Netherlands and UK).
- Attendance to the [ONE EU](#), the conference organised by EFSA in 2022 in Brussels with a poster presentation.
- Attendance to the 6th [World One Health Congress](#) with a poster presentation.

Participation to additional educational activities *such as*:

- [23 Things International](#), a global and collaborative online programme that provide researchers to online research tools for all disciplines, and profile-building opportunities.
- [RX One Health](#) field course, a field-based experiential learning course focused on One Health core competencies organised by the University of California, Davis.
- [Doctoral workshop](#), an event for doctoral students on the field of environmental health, organized by La Cité della Solidarité, Geneva health forum and UNITAR.

11. Added value and benefits during PhD resulting from being part of the OHEJP doctoral programme and consortium

- Dissemination of achievements and results, which helped a lot to give relevance and visibility to the project by the excellent dissemination of the communications team.
- Continuous learning: many learning opportunities such as cogwheel workshops and scientific meetings.

- Contribution to the development of interpersonal skills, with special place laid presentations skills with the PhD students given the chance to present their research and participate to the 3 minute thesis competition.
- Networking: easy interaction and networking with other projects, PhDs from other institutions, and international organizations. Thanks to the OHEJP consortium, during the ASM 2022, I met the collaborators of the Netherlands where I did a short-term mission; and participated to the Doctoral Workshop, organised by “La Cité della Solidarité Internationale” and the collaboration of the United Nations in Geneva.
- Funding that allowed the attendance to conferences and relevant courses.

12. Transferrable skills and Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Demonstrating in Laboratories	Teaching	29/01/2020	University of Surrey – Degree for Higher Education
Assessment and Feedback	Teaching	03/02/2020	University of Surrey – Degree for Higher Education
Workshop on Git	IT	04/02/2020	University of Surrey
Introduction to Teaching in Higher Education	Teaching	07/02/2020	University of Surrey – Degree for Higher Education
Introduction to HPC	IT	24/02/2020	University of Surrey
Presentation skills	Communication	12/02/2020 19/02/2020	University of Surrey - ELSP
Intermediate R	IT Coding	20/05/2020 - 22/05/2020	Datacamp
Infectious disease modelling	Research Modelling	01/06/2020 - 12/06/2020	Coursera - Imperial College
Introduction to Infectious Disease Modelling and its Applications	Research Modelling	15/06/2020 - 26/06/2020	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
Statistics and R	IT	07/10/2020 – 17/10/2020	Coursera- HarvardX
French B2	Languages	07/11/2020 - 28/04/2021	University of Surrey – GGA
Managing your supervisor	Communication	15/12/2020	University of Surrey – Doctoral College RDP
Genomics & Bioinformatics workshop	Research Bioinformatics	14/12/2020- 24/12/2020	University of Surrey – Arnoud van Vliet
Research Data Management and Open Data	Research	19/01/2021	University of Surrey – Library Learning Services
Digital innovation for One Health practitioners	Research	15/02/2021- 19/02/2021	OHEJP CPD Workshop
Versatile Emerging Infectious disease Observatory (VEO)	Research	25/02/2021	OHEJP Cogwheel workshop
Building your professional network workshop	Communication	19/03/2021	University of Surrey – Doctoral College RDP

Performing Data analysis in R studio	IT Coding	26/03/2021	University of Surrey - Academic Skills and Development
Public engagement Workshop	Communication	01/04/2022	University of Surrey
The Conversation media training	Communication	20/04/2021	University of Surrey – Doctoral college
Storytelling for researchers	Communication	10/05/2021	University of Surrey - ESRC Impact Acceleration Account
Communication with impact	Communication	12/05/2021	University of Surrey - ESRC Impact Acceleration Account
German A1	Languages	05/10/2021-31/03/2022	University of Surrey – GGA
Introduction to Git	IT	27/05/2022	University of Surrey – Open Reproducibility Society
LaTeX for academic documents	IT	28/10/2022	University of Surrey – Open Reproducibility Society
Demonstrator of practical sessions	Teaching	03/2020-12/2022	University of Surrey
Research assistant collaboration	Research Lab work skills	10/2021 – 01/2022	University of Surrey
One Health conference (online)	Research	03-11-2022-04-11-2022	University of Galway
How to influence policy seminar	Soft skills	08-11-2022	Skill-Influence - UoS
Viva exam workshop	Research	05-12-2022	University of Surrey - Doctoral College

13. Ethical Reviews

Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments PhD Project Supervisor, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2020
NA	NA	NA

14. Scientific Publications

A comprehensive publication is under final revisions and ready to be submitted to Nature Climate Change (or alternatively to Lancet Planetary Health). It consists on a summary on the whole methodology of thesis with its two main applications: checking the universal effect of weather found for UK in the Netherlands, as well as the climate change projections.

15. Additional Outputs

- *Poster presentations on the progress of the EnvDis project at:*
 - *6th World One Health Conference, 2020.*
 - *ASM2020, poster and 3-Minute thesis competition.*
 - *ASM2021, poster and 3-Minute thesis competition.*
 - *ASM2022, poster and 3-Minute thesis competition.*
 - *ONE EU Conference 2022.*
- *Oral presentation on the final results of EnvDis at the Faculty of Health and Medical Science at the University of Surrey 2023.*
- *Short flash talks at the Research celebration events of the University of Surrey in 2020, 2021 and 2022.*
- *Participation to the 3-Minute thesis competition, University of Surrey 2021.*
- *Participation on “Your thesis as a poem”, within the Academic Writing Month, University of Surrey 2021: <https://twitter.com/SurreyDocCol/status/1468150842159255556?t=1ne0Stsit-Gikz0vG73Viq&s=08>*

16. Specific outcomes to highlight in dissemination and communications

I am very proud of the applicability of the methodology of EnvDis to different geographic locations, such as the Netherlands, which reinforces the universal effect of the weather factors combinations explored in EnvDis. A research visit was approved with collaborators from New Zealand to test the methodology in a country from the southern hemisphere and weather conditions more diverse from the UK, but unfortunately did not materialized due to the COVID-19 related travel restrictions. I would like to encourage Health Ministries of other countries to participate in feeding the model with epidemiology and weather data so that the predictive power of the conditional incidence can be strengthened.

17. One Health impact

The model developed in this thesis describes the effect that weather has in salmonellosis incidence conditional to specific weather factors. It helps to formulate theories around the mechanism underlying the interface seasonality-disease. As future research, we recommend a complementary mechanistic approach where the effect of the different weather variables acts in the biologic processes of Salmonella are available. The conditional incidence could be applied in conjunction with in-depth experimental and social research to infer robust mechanistic theories.

EnvDis has contributed to the existing knowledge on *Salmonella*, providing great insight into the mechanism of seasonality underlying the final reporting of cases, such as population behaviour and environmental effects on host and pathogen. To date, this is the first study that analyses the interconnected effect of weather factors on the risk of salmonellosis in the context of climate change. This information could be used by health professionals and Public Health officers to be more alert to the potential increase in cases and outbreaks at unusual times of the year, allowing early detection and preventive measures to be taken. The model allows to estimate salmonellosis notifications based on weather forecast. If other diseases especially relevant to weather variation, this model could assist in better preparedness in the event of new or extreme weather events.

By utilizing the provided open-source code, this methodology can be applied where long-term, high-resolution surveillance data is available, making it suitable for other countries and infectious agents. Incorporating animal disease data would be highly beneficial and serve as an ideal complement to surveillance data, considering the interdependencies between human and animal health. This integration would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the overall disease landscape and facilitate a holistic approach to health monitoring and control. Therefore, we encourage health institutions of other countries to actively participate in sharing surveillance data and applying the model to their area. Such collaboration and data sharing will enrich the model with broader information, thereby enhancing the robustness and reliability of the model's conclusions. A first application of the model was carried out successfully during the short-term mission in the Netherlands. The idea was well-received, demonstrating that one month is sufficient to evaluate the model's performance in a different location through collaborative efforts. At the same time, we are aware of the interest that the climate change application is generating and we are expecting high interest when the work is published.

Upon integrating robust datasets from diverse geographic locations into the model, it becomes feasible to incorporate automated applications, such as R Shiny, into regular national surveillance systems. This integration would enable swift risk identification during unexpected weather conditions. The implications for the One Health approach are self-explanatory, as the model has demonstrated that the environment plays a fundamental role in disease dynamics. By highlighting these connections, the model reinforces the importance of adopting a holistic and collaborative approach to disease prevention, surveillance, and control within a One Health framework.

18. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	Annual Scientific Meeting 2020. Presentation of poster and participation in 3-minute Thesis competition.		
Date:	27-29 May 2020		
Place:	virtual		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	750	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Vet School Research Celebration Event. University of Surrey		
Date:	09 Sep 2020		
Place:	virtual		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	

Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	120	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Communication and Media Workshop (OHEJP)		
Date:	05-06 June 2020		
Place:	virtual		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	750	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	

General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	6th World One Health Congress		
Date:	30 Oct -3 Nov 2020		
Place:	virtual		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	~1500	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	6th Cogwheel Workshop (SafeConsume/OHEJP)		
Date:	25 Nov 2020		
Place:	virtual		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	

Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	40	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 – poster presentation and three minute thesis competition		
Date:	09-11/06/2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Cogwheel workshop – Versatile Emerging Infectious Disease Observatory (VEO)		
Date:	25/02/21		
Place:	Virtual/ Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) & Norwegian Veterinary Institute		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	55	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Vet School Research Symposium		
Date:	01/07/2021 - 02/07/2021		
Place:	Virtual/ Vet School University of Surrey		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	

Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	75	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Modelling in Animal Health conference (ModAH ²)		
Date:	16/09/2021		
Place:	Virtual/ INRAe		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	32	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Workshop: Integrated approaches to zoonoses: a systems thinking primer
Date:	08/10/2021

Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	20	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 – poster presentation and three-minute thesis competition		
Date:	11-13/04/2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy.		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	

Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	150	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	ONE EU Conference (organised by EFSA). Poster presentation		
Date:	21-24/06/2022		
Place:	Brussels, Belgium		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	600	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Doctoral workshop in Environmental Health		
Date:	16/01/2023		
Place:	Geneva, Switzerland		

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.

	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	Yes
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories

	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	20	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	5		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Summer School. Environmental Issues in One Health: from risk assessment to surveillance
Date:	26/07-06/08/2021
Place:	Online

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.

	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	

Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Final School: Sustainability in One Health: how can it be achieved?		
Date:	05-07/12/2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	Yes
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	RX One Health Field Institute
Date:	18/06-01/07/2023
Place:	California, USA.

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.

	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories

	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public	2,000	Other	
Policy Makers			